

Combination of Animal Physiology Studies With Microbiology In Creating Antioxidant Drinks To Counteract Free Radicals

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Animal Physiology is a branch of biology that discusses body functions in the form of tissues and organs, all of which work synergistically to maintain homeostasis. In addition, studying animal physiology can also lead someone to discover new things related to economic discoveries, such as testing plant extracts for the cure of a disease with observable results based on histopathological studies. According to my assumption, the field of animal physiology is very dynamic along with the times and also has wide relevance to other branches of biological science. One of the branches of biology whose integration is compatible with animal physiology is microbiology. The scope of microbiology is also very broad regarding the use and discovery of species of fungi and bacteria. So far, the discovery of bacterial and fungal species is still limited to knowing the name, the habitat found, and their use. However, seeing physiologically has not been thoroughly studied.

Research that often appears in microbiology is the use of bacteria to ferment food and beverages. The drink that I think is interesting to study more is Kombucha, which has benefits especially as a source of antioxidants. Antioxidants are found in the form of compounds that are able to neutralize or as inhibitors of free radicals and prevent degenerative diseases and repair cells, proteins and fats damaged by exposure to free radicals (Parwata, 2016). Antioxidants consist of two kinds, endogenous antioxidants (which are produced from the body) and exogenous (which are obtained from eating foods and drinks that contain antioxidants). In the body, antioxidants have 3 types of enzymes, namely Superoxide Dismutase (SOD), Glutathione Peroxidase (GSHPx) and catalase. SOD works as an anti-inflammatory and glutathione peroxidase works to move H₂O₂ along with lipid peroxide assisted by ions in transition metals, The explanation regarding the mechanism of action of these two enzymes is very complex (Khaira, 2010).

Nowadays, which is filled with changing lifestyles such as eating junk food/fast food, smoking, high air pollution, exposure to UV rays, exposure to toxic substances such as pesticides, etc. can generate free radicals through autoxidation and excessive synthesis of *Reactive Oxygen Species*. Free radicals are compounds in the form of reactive oxygen which are filled with unpaired electrons, therefore electrons from reactive oxygen can bind very strongly with other substances and are unstable. Actually free radicals are needed in the body to fight inflammation, kill bacteria and regulate

body tone. smooth muscle with a certain amount, although it is needed if too much is found in the body is also not good but becomes toxic to the body and causes various types of inflammation and disease, most diseases in humans arise due to too much exposure to various types of free radicals (Sayuti and Rina, 2015). Many diseases arise from oxidative stress due to exposure to free radicals such as atherosclerosis, neurodegenerative diseases, such as Parkinson's or Alzheimer's disease, or even obesity, in order to maintain a balance between production and removal of reactive oxygen species, it is important to find easily accessible sources of antioxidants. Oxidative stress is closely related to systemic inflammatory processes, endothelial cell proliferation, apoptosis, and vasoconstriction. Oxidative stress has a role in the occurrence of various diseases, especially degenerative diseases such as cancer, diabetes mellitus, atherosclerosis which is the cause of coronary heart disease or heart failure (Rani and Yadav, 2015).

Kombucha is a fermented beverage from a sweet medium whose history comes from Japan, generally using black tea, green tea and roselle. Kombucha starters generally use cultures of acetic acid bacteria (*Gluconobacter*, *Acetobacter* species), lactic acid bacteria (*Lactobacillus*, *Lactococcus* species) and yeast (*Saccharomyces ludwigia*, *Zygosaccharomyces bailii* etc.) which are fermented for 14 days (Villarreal-Soto et al. 2018). This drink has a distinctive taste, namely sweet and sour with a sparkling sensation. In Microbiology, the manufacture of fermented kombucha drinks has been studied using different media. The results of research from Nur et. al (2018) who tested several alkaloids for making kombucha tea products, consisting of coffee leaves, cocoa leaves, ground coffee, cocoa powder with green tea and black tea as controls. The results showed that the total number of *A. xylinum* bacteria was more abundant in cocoa leaves because in this sample the sugar nutrients needed by *A. xylinum* bacteria were met with the appropriate amount so that the fermentation results were good. lowest pH compared to other media. Currently, the trend of fermented drinks is indeed more popular besides being useful as probiotics, prebiotics and synbiotics can also ward off free radicals. Kombucha, the fermented tea, has strong antioxidant properties associated with high polyphenol content, particularly flavonoids. Therefore, it should be consumed by people particularly exposed to oxidative stress. The antioxidant activity of kombucha is diverse and depends on the type and composition of the tea infusion before fermentation and on the content of SCOBY, which determines the character of the forming metabolites and conditions the type of the forming products of polyphenol compound transformation. A particularly rich source of antioxidants, especially flavonoids, are red and green tea types on the 1st and 14th day of fermentation. Therefore, the selection of tea other than black tea, and the subsequent subjection to fermentation, are beneficial to human health (Jakubczyk et. al, 2020). In addition to using the previous ingredients, you can also use other materials

that have a broader function, such as yam. The yam plant (*Pachyrhizus erosus*) is a plant that contains dietary fiber so it has the potential as a synbiotic drink. Jicama is known to contain lipophilic flavonoids which can damage microbial membranes (Supari et al., 2016). According to Zakiy et.al (2017) the flavonoid content will be a problem if jicama is used as a synbiotic drink, but the flavonoid content can be removed by heating, so making yam as a synbiotic fermented drink is very possible. In addition to its function as an antibiotic, jicama also plays a role in suppressing metabolic diseases, according to the results of research by Santoso et. al (2019) who used yam fiber to see the effectiveness of natural *P. erosus* Fiber (PEF) in suppressing the development of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) caused by excessive intake of high-sugar diet (HSD), with the findings that supplementation of 25% PEF sustained the normal morphological feature of the liver in HSD-fed mice. Moreover, PEF also prevented the development of microvesicles in the liver tissue, nuclear shrinkage, and hepatolysis as indicators of liver disease. So that PEF can be recommended to be used as a powerful supplementary diet to prevent metabolic diseases caused by HSD (High-Sugar Diet). The latest discovery of yam can be used as a reference for researching if yam fiber is used as a medium for making kombucha, whether it can be used as a combination of drinks with various benefits, which of course must be investigated first with experimental animals.

Because the need for antioxidants in the body is so important to ward off free radicals, one way to do this is by consuming fermented drinks that contain antioxidants such as kombucha. The results from several journals say that the antioxidant level of kombucha is quite high, this can be used as research material in the field of animal physiology how the effect on diseases caused by oxidative stress and damage to cell and organ structures from humans, whether it can heal damage and disease or not must be observed through the histological structure or seen with the help of sophisticated tools such as using an electron microscope as an example to see the effect of kombucha drink on liver cell repair. The use of other ingredients that contain alkaloids can also be used to make kombucha fermentation such as cocoa leaves and coffee leaves and powder which of course must be investigated more deeply the effects of using coffee media for the body whether the body's response is good or even has a long effect because coffee contains caffeine . Caffeine can increase human motor activity that causes sleeplessness and disrupts the body's circadian rhythm, all of which cannot be separated from the ability of caffeine to affect neurotransmitters in the basal ganglia in the brain with a group of subcortical nuclei involved in various aspects of the body's motor activity (Fisone 2004). To see if there is an effect of caffeine contained in coffee grounds on fermented kombucha, it is necessary to conduct research that leads to the human nervous system as well as other organs such as the heart which of course requires an understanding of the field of animal physiology.

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